

SHORT NOTES

(±)1-*p*-Hydroxyphenylbutan-3-ol and Some Derivatives

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Betuligenol, one of the rare naturally occurring phenolic alcohols, having interesting biochemical properties¹, has been assigned the structure (–) 1-*p*-hydroxyphenylbutan-3-ol^{2,3}. Delphin and Sosa⁴ synthesised (±) 1-*p*-methoxyphenylbutan-3-ol, resolved it, and proved the identity of the (–) isomer with the methyl ether of natural betuligenol.

Although (±) 1-*p*-hydroxyphenylbutan-3-ol has already been synthesised⁵, it has not yet been resolved to the natural isomer. Our attempts to do so through its 1-menthoxyacetic ester also failed because it proved to be a liquid. Attempts to resolve by the hydrogen phthalate method did not meet with success either. As the racemic alcohol required for our work was obtained by a different route, we wish to record its synthesis and preparation of some hitherto-unreported derivatives. Condensation of *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde with ethyl acetoacetate in presence of piperidine gave ethyl α-*p*-hydroxybenzylideneacetoacetate which, on catalytic hydrogenation over Pd-C, gave ethyl α-*p*-hydroxybenzylacetoacetate. On ketonic hydrolysis, 1-*p*-hydroxyphenylbutan-3-one was obtained. Reduction with sodium borohydride gave (±) 1-*p*-hydroxyphenylbutan-3-ol, m.p. 72° (lit⁵. m.p. 70-71°).

Ethyl α-p-Hydroxybenzylidene acetoacetate (I).—A solution of *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (10 g.), ethyl acetoacetate (11 ml), ethanol (10 ml), and piperidine (0.3 ml) was held at 70° (bath temp.) for 2 hours. On being kept overnight in an ice-chest, it deposited *ethyl α-p-hydroxybenzylideneacetoacetate* (7.1 g.) as yellow needles. Further amount (1 g.) was recovered by diluting the mother liquor and keeping it in an ice-chest for several days. Recrystallisation from aqueous methanol yielded the pure product, m. p. 140°. It gives the characteristic deep yellow coloration of the chalkone with aqueous NaOH. (Found: C, 65.9; H, 5.6. C₁₃H₁₄O₄ requires C, 66.6; H, 5.98%).

Ethyl α-p-Hydroxybenzylacetoacetate (II)—The preceding ester (5 g.), dissolved in methanol (70 ml), was treated with Pd—C (1%, 2g., 20 ml) under atmospheric pressure until 640 ml of hydrogen was absorbed. The solution was filtered, methanol evaporated, and the light brown oily residue was distilled in *vacuo* [2.5 mm/225-30° (bath)] to yield *ethyl α-p-*

1. Lederer, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 2115.
2. Sosa, *Ann. chim.*, 1940, 14, 5.
3. Lederer and Polonsky, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Biol.*, 1942, 24, 1396.
4. *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1942, 9, 771.
5. Zemplén *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1944, 77B, 784.

hydroxybenzylacetate in almost quantitative yield as colorless, thick oil which did not solidify on keeping in an ice chest. (No yellow coloration with aqueous NaOH).

It was characterised as 4-*p*-hydroxybenzyl-3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone, obtained by refluxing an ethanolic solution (20 ml) of the ester (0.6 g.) with phenylhydrazine hydrochloride (0.5 g.) and sodium acetate (0.5g.) for 2 hours. It was crystallised from dilute ethanol in prismatic needles, m.p. 210°. (Found: N, 9.8. $C_{17}H_{16}O_2N_2$ requires N, 10.0%).

1-*p*-Hydroxyphenylbutan-3-one(III).—A solution of the ester (II)(10 g.) in 5% aqueous NaOH (95 ml) was kept at room temperature for 24 hours and then treated with 50% H_2SO_4 (40 ml) when CO_2 evolved briskly with separation of a brown oil. The mixture was refluxed for 8 hours, cooled, and extracted with ether; the extract was washed with aqueous $NaHCO_3$ and water and dried ($MgSO_4$). Evaporation of the ether gave the ketone (5.2 g.) as brown, long needles, which on recrystallisation from a large volume of water with a little ethanol yielded the pure product as shining white needles, m.p. 82.5°. (Found: C, 72.8; H, 7.1. $C_{10}H_{12}O_2$ requires 73.1; H 7.3%).

The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, prepared in the usual way, was crystallised from ethanol as red needles, m.p. 145°. (Found: N, 16.3. $C_{16}H_{16}O_5N_4$ requires N, 16.28%).

The *p*-nitrobenzoate derivative was crystallised from dilute ethanol as prisms, m.p. 105°. (Found: C, 64.7; H, 4.2. $C_{17}H_{15}O_3N$ requires C, 65.1; H, 4.7%).

(±) 1-*p*-Hydroxyphenylbutan-3-ol (IV).—A solution of the ketone (III) (1 g.) in *N*-NaOH solution (7 ml) was added to $NaBH_4$ (0.1 g.) in water (1.5 ml) and heated to 60-70° for 2 hours. It was cooled, acidified with HCl (dil.) when the brown oil separating solidified; m.p. 60°, on being kept in an ice chest. It was taken in excess boiling petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) with addition of a little ethyl acetate to effect a clear solution; on being kept in an ice chest over a period of several days the butanol crystallised in white prisms (0.3 g.), m.p. 72° (lit³. m.p. 70-71°). (Found: C, 71.8; H, 8.1. Calc. for $C_{10}H_{14}O_2$: C, 72.3; H, 8.4%).

On shaking an acetone solution of the above butanol with benzoyl chloride in presence of aqueous NaOH, (±) 1-*p*-benzoyloxyphenylbutan-3-ol was obtained. It was crystallised from petroleum ether (40-60°) as shining plates, m. p. 68.5°. (Found: C, 74.9; H, 6.9. $C_{17}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 75.5; H, 6.6%).

(±) 1-*p*-(*p*-Nitrobenzoyloxy)phenylbutan-3-ol was prepared by the same method using *p*-nitrobenzoyl chloride. It was crystallised from dilute ethanol in prismatic needles, m.p. 100°. (Found: C, 64.8; H, 5.6. $C_{17}H_{17}O_5N$ requires C, 64.76; H, 5.4%).

A solution of (±) 1-*p*-hydroxyphenylbutan-3-ol in anhydrous pyridine was treated with *p*-nitrobenzoyl chloride and warmed to effect a clear solution. Next day, it was poured into excess water and the precipitated solid was crystallised from ethanol to yield the *di-p*-nitrobenzoate as prismatic needles, m.p. 145°. (Found: C, 61.4; H, 4.6. $C_{24}H_{20}O_8N_2$ requires C, 62.1; H, 4.3%).